

1 **Nuclear transport of protein and RNA cargoes is altered during TE commitment.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 nuclear transport machinery as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo. This included Kapna2, which functions in transport of protein cargoes with classical NLSs.
11 The findings demonstrate specific changes in cellular transport during a discrete stage of embryonic
12 development, during lineage commitment of stem cells to the trophectoderm.

13 Citations

14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
1. Li, X., Sun, L. and Jin, Y., 2008. Identification of karyopherin-alpha 2 as an Oct4 associated
protein. *Journal of Genetics and Genomics*, 35(12), pp.723-728.